

The role and importance of musical education in the elementary grades of general education schools

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Abstract: The article gives instructions on the role of music in the development of musical literacy and aesthetic education of young people through music education in secondary schools. Also, in the process of music education today, the increasing interest and passion of students in the art of music and the importance of this art in the spiritual development of young people are highlighted.

Key words: Music culture, aesthetic education, national culture, educational institutions, national values.

The spiritual growth of our country in many ways requires a deep understanding of the restoration of our national values, a wide-scale promotion with a feeling of heart, and most importantly, the education of the young generation. In this regard, our musical values have a special place. In particular, songs and songs belonging to Uzbek folk music are truly priceless spiritual treasures of our people.

Music, with its unique nature, has the power to greatly influence the spiritual world of students. After all, under the influence of melody and melody, the growth of the emotional world, the formation of perception and thinking, the desire for goodness, the love of beauty, the preservation of nature, and the desire to serve for the prosperity of the family and the Motherland will increase. Music education is one of the main and complex aspects of the education of sophistication, it teaches to correctly perceive and appreciate the beautiful things around. "Music has the power

to have a certain moral effect on the soul, and since music has such a quality, it should be included among the subjects of educating young people," said the great ancient Greek philosopher Aristotle.¹ educating students through musical education requires a unique pedagogical approach.

Thanks to the independence of Uzbekistan, we restored our spiritual heritage based on the rich historical values of our great ancestors, our unique and attractive culture spanning thousands of years. There is another very important basis for improving the development of our society, as well as economic and political factors, without which it is impossible to strengthen independence, build a free and prosperous Motherland, and build a free and prosperous society. Along with economic and political reforms, independence requires fundamental changes in people's consciousness and worldview, manners, faith, knowledge level, mentality, culture and spirituality.

The main purpose of music lessons in secondary schools is to instill in students the ability to learn the art of music based on the laws of beauty and to develop a musical culture in them. The purpose of the teacher is to develop musical-artistic taste, moral-aesthetic feelings in students, to develop their creative abilities, to increase their interest in the art of music and the artistic need in their musical activities, to form a culture of musical literacy, through music sets a number of tasks, such as creating an understanding that it is an expression of human feelings and hopes. In order to instill love and passion for music in students, to increase their level of music, singing and extracurricular activities in the field of music should be strengthened in every way. Each of the elementary and middle classes of schools should have choral groups, and musical instruments should be available in school classes with facilities. At the same time, it is necessary to pay attention to teaching music to students individually, to involve parents and the public in this work. The

musical knowledge and skills acquired at school should be used in everyday life, at musical evenings at school, at music and art festivals, and when going on excursions.

Today, music plays an important role in the formation of a person; actively affects his emotions and psyche. Bringing from the basic conditions of general schools to the world of sophistication and giving spiritual education. In this, the teacher introduces the children to an important piece of music and plays it expressively "live", attracting the attention of the students, developing their speech, thinking ability, broadening their world view, emotional feelings as well actively affects. The content of music lessons involves not only mastering, but also the development of students' consciousness, attitude to reality, the formation of aesthetic culture and the formation of other internal feelings. zaims to:

seeks new methods and tools in music education.

represents the inextricable connection between life and art.

In order to achieve these goals, the teacher should prepare seriously, work tirelessly on himself, that is, improve the ways of improving his consciousness by going to scientific literature, theater, places of interest to increase his knowledge. It is important that the classroom where music lessons are conducted is well equipped. Technical tools, methodical visual aids should be equipped with piano instruments and Uzbek folk instruments, lesson plans should be created using the program, and new technologies should be used. Thus, it is required that the purpose and content of all the activities of the music lessons should illuminate the contents of the lesson and connect all parts of the lesson with each other. To perfect the musical culture of elementary school students and to develop their musical literacy skills at a higher level is one of the urgent tasks today. One of the most important factors in the implementation of these tasks is to achieve deep mastery of the students' initial musical-theoretical knowledge.

Deep and perfect mastery of the initial musical-theoretical knowledge given in the lessons effectively affects their ability to sing, to consciously perceive and analyze music while listening to it. Therefore, in each lesson, it is necessary to pay attention and monitor students not only to develop their skills and abilities related to singing and listening to music, but also to their deep and perfect mastery of musical-theoretical knowledge.

At the present time, which is full of development and changes in our republic, the all-round development of young people is the demand and need of the time. Educating the young generation to be spiritually strong, educated, and full of pride in our independent Motherland is an urgent topic of our time. This is one of the complex and large-scale problems facing education.

Education means raising a person who is mature in all respects, who embodies moral purity, spiritual wealth and physical integrity. Music plays a leading role in the educational system. Nowadays, the role of music and art in human education is increasing. Undoubtedly, the role of music education in raising our young people as spiritually mature and perfect people is great. The school inculcates the basics of knowledge in young people. It serves as the main foundation for the formation and strengthening of the child's scientific outlook.

Therefore, the main goal of primary music education and training in the elementary grades of general education schools is to instill in students the ability to learn the art of music based on the laws of beauty and to instill in them a musical culture. Music culture lessons in primary grades are an integral part of the moral-aesthetic education system of general education. Accordingly, the organization of classes starting from the 1st grade on a consistent, systematic and scientific basis ensures that students and young people go to the next stages of education with certain preparation.

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